

Dachorganisation des akademischen Mittelbaus in der Schweiz
Organisation faîtière du corps intermédiaire académique en Suisse
Federazione delle organizzazioni del corps intermedio in Svizzera
Umbrella organisation of academic mid-level staff in Switzerland

Swiss-Wide Mental Health Survey (SWiMS) 2024: National Report

a survey initiated and conducted by actionuni

Key Takeaways:

- Survey of 2,518 academic mid-level staff across 13 Swiss institutions
- 22% meet criteria for problematic depressive symptoms
- 53% lack awareness of available mental health resources; 67% doubt their effectiveness
- 39% are "completely" stressed about career uncertainty (59% among postdocs)
- Staff without permanent contracts show worse mental health and higher stress
- 61% are rather satisfied with their job

Executive Summary

The Swiss-Wide Mental Health Survey (SWiMS) 2024 explores the mental health and well-being of academic mid-level staff in Switzerland, including doctoral researchers, postdoctoral researchers, and other academic staff not in professorial positions (see figure on p.11 for details). It includes responses from 2,518 individuals across 13 Swiss higher education institutions. While the sample is too small to be considered fully representative of all academic mid-level staff in Switzerland, the report points to clear trends and highlights both strengths and challenges faced by mid-level staff.

Concerning Levels of Key Mental Health Indicators

The survey data suggest concerning levels of key mental health indicators. 17% of the respondents perceive their mental health as poor or very poor. Additionally, 22% meet the criteria for problematic levels of depressive symptoms based on established standards. 24% report of feeling burned out from work at least once a week. 21% report experiencing high levels of stress, including persistent anxiety, restlessness, or sleep disturbances. Nearly a quarter (23%) have frequently considered quitting their jobs due to the work environment in the past year.

The majority of respondents report low awareness and confidence in the mental health resources available at their institution. Specifically, 53% indicated they do not have a clear understanding of the mental health resources and services offered, while 67% expressed doubt that these resources can actually help them.

Stress Driven by Uncertainty and Lack of Support

A considerable portion of respondents report experiencing stress and negative perceptions related to their work environment: 39% report being “completely” stressed about uncertainty regarding their next career step (especially postdocs with 59%). Additionally, 30% cite a lack of support from their supervisor as a source of stress. Half of the respondents (50%) feel completely or moderately stressed due to a lack of confidence in their professional skills. Furthermore, 40% do not feel confident that their institution or workplace would listen and take action if they raised a concern. Issues related to discrimination are also prevalent: 18% have personally experienced bullying, discrimination, or harassment in the past year, and 55% have heard of such incidents happening to others in their workplace.

High Levels of Job Satisfaction and Creative Fulfillment

Despite these challenges, several positive aspects of the work environment were identified. 61% of respondents report being rather satisfied with their job (scoring >4 on a 7-point scale). A majority, 66%, feel that creativity is welcomed at their institution or workplace. Additionally, 57% state that their workplace enables them to focus on their research and career. Moreover, 71% indicate that their working group fosters a collaborative culture, highlighting key strengths that institutions can build upon.

Populations Most at Risk

Certain groups within the academic and research community appear to be particularly vulnerable to poor mental health outcomes. Individuals without a permanent contract report lower levels of general mental health, and higher levels of depressive symptoms and stress. Similarly, internationals—those without Swiss citizenship or a C-permit—experience lower general mental health and elevated stress. Additionally, participants who do not identify as either male or female, though a small proportion (1.7%), report generally lower mental health and higher exposure to stressors.

Conclusion

The SWiMS 2024 data indicate a sector under strain. While many mid-level academics find satisfaction and support in their work, a significant portion face mental health challenges and job insecurity. Addressing these issues is not only a matter of individual well-being but of academic excellence and sustainability. Coordinated national action is essential to ensure that Swiss academia remains a healthy, inclusive, and innovative environment for all.

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Introduction

The Swiss-Wide Mental Health Survey (SWiMS) 2024 explores the mental health and well-being of academic mid-level staff in Switzerland, including doctoral researchers, postdoctoral researchers, and other academic staff not in professorial positions (see figure on p.11 for details). The survey aims to identify key challenges in working conditions and research environments, providing a data-driven foundation for improving policies and support systems at Swiss higher education institutions.

This report presents the national-level findings, offering descriptive data into mental health outcomes, stressors, available resources, sources of discrimination, and questionable research practices. Each of the 13 participating institution also received an institution-specific report, in which the responses of the specific institution are compared to all other part-taking institutions combined.

Background and motivation

Academic mid-level staff are essential to research, teaching, and student supervision, making up approximately 48% of the academic workforce in Switzerland (Federal Statistical Office, 2024). The mid-level faculty thus makes a decisive contribution to the innovative strength and competitiveness of the university system as well as to the quality of teaching and training.

Despite their central role, academic mid-level staff are often exposed to a variety of stresses. The work pressure is high due to the demands of research, teaching and administrative tasks (Barkhuizen, Rothmann, and Van de Vijver 2014; Mattijssen et al. 2020). Added to this is the increasing pressure to publish, reinforced by the “publish or perish” principle, which has a significant influence on academic careers (Miller, Taylor, and Bedeian 2011; Tijdink, Verbeke, and Smulders 2013). Many early career researchers also struggle with the uncertainty of their professional future, as most positions are temporary and the prospect of a long-term academic career is very limited (Petersen et al. 2012; Nagy et al. 2019; Guidetti et al. 2022).

These factors in the academic environment can have a negative impact on the mental health of early career researchers (Bolotnyy, Basilico, and Barreira 2022; Urbina-Garcia 2020). International studies show that 30–40% of researchers suffer from mental health problems (Divaris et al. 2012; Gloria and Steinhardt 2016; Levecque et al. 2017; Evans et al. 2018; Mattijssen et al. 2020; Estupiñá et al. 2024). Other international studies also document high rates of burnout (9%), depression (17–24%) and anxiety (17%) among early career researchers (Bolotnyy, Basilico, and Barreira 2022; Boone et al. 2022; Evans et al. 2018; Satinsky et al. 2021). In the long term, this jeopardizes the quality of research and the innovative strength of universities (Amer et al. 2022; Barry et al. 2018).

Despite growing awareness of these issues internationally, Switzerland lacks comprehensive national data on the mental health of academic mid-level staff. While some institutions have conducted internal surveys (e.g., ETH Zurich’s employee survey), a coordinated, nationwide effort has been missing that allows identification of national and local areas of improvement. The last nationwide report on the working conditions of academic mid-level staff in Switzerland was conducted – also by actionuni – in 2009 (see SBFI report here).

The Swiss-Wide Mental Health Survey (SWiMS)

To address this gap, actionuni, in collaboration with 13 academic mid-level staff associations, launched SWiMS 2024 as a bottom-up initiative. The survey was developed jointly by the actionuni survey team and representatives of academic mid-level staff associations, and formally approved at the actionuni General Assembly in late 2023. The survey provides a nationwide assessment of mental health among academic mid-level staff in Switzerland, highlighting both stressors and protective factors.

Participation in the survey was entirely anonymous and voluntary, and respondents could withdraw at any time during the process. Ethical approval was obtained from the ethics Committee of the Faculty of Philosophy of the University of Zurich (nr. 23.12.07). Data was collected between May 13th and October 31st 2024. The survey was conducted in English only.

Detailed survey content and codebook

Detailed item formulations, variables, etc. can be found in the codebook and survey-PDF on the OSF repository of this project: <https://osf.io/kqdnm>.

Sharing of raw data

As resources for preparing the data for open access are currently unavailable, it is possible that a public release of anonymized raw data may not take place. For this reason, the present report provides a detailed overview of the findings – spanning more than 200 pages – to provide broad accessibility of the results.

How to read the key plots

Distribution plots

Grouped questions plots

Sample Description

Data cleaning

Only institutions with more than 10 responses were considered in this report. 43 participants of 16 institution with a mean of 2.7 (SD = 1.81) participants were removed from the dataset. 62 additional responses were removed because institution “Other” (n = 44), “Prefer not to say” (n = 15), or were missing (n = 3) were indicated. We also excluded participants that took shorter than 4 minutes to respond (n = 4). In total, 2518 responses were part of this report. Responses numbers in the different plots may vary due to missing responses on a particular question or on grouping variables (e.g., age category).

Parttaking institutions and response counts

Total count: 2518
 Only institutions with more than 10 participants are displayed.

The average duration of responding to the survey was 18.01 minutes (SD = 12.96).

Demographics

The figures below summarize the key demographic characteristics of all part-taking institutions.

Age

Question: 'What is your age?', with answer options: 18-30 ; 31-40 ; 41-60 ; > 60 ; Prefer not to say.

For the subsequent analyses this variable was grouped into three categories: "18-30," "31-40," and ">41." Respondents unwilling to disclose their age were coded as missing.

Gender

Question: 'What is the gender you identify yourself with? (select all that apply)' with answer options "male","female","non-binary", or "prefer not to say".

Recoded from multiple binary selections into categories: "male," "female," or "other" (including nonbinary or multiple selections). "prefer not to say" responses were coded as missing.

Research Discipline

Question: 'What is your research discipline?'

Subsequently referred to as "Natural Sciences and Engineering", "Medicine", "Social Sciences", and "Humanities". "Prefer not to say" responses coded as missing.

Position Type

Question: 'What is your current main position?'

Recoded positions into four broad groups: "Researcher aiming for a PhD.", "Postdoctoral researcher", "Other researchers with a PhD", and "Other". "Prefer not to say" responses coded as missing. The group "Other researchers with a PhD" consisted of categories "Researcher above postdoc (habilitated or equivalent)", "Other researchers with a PhD". The group "Other" consisted of categories "Supportive positions (e.g., administrative personnel, technical staff)" and "Lecturing only".

Funding Source

Question: 'How is your main position funded?'

Original funding categories simplified into three groups: "SNSF", "Non-SNSF funding", and "University/Higher education institute." Ambiguous or undisclosed funding sources coded as missing.

Residence Status

Question: 'What type of residence status do you have?'

Subsequently used with residence status reduced to two groups: "Swiss citizenship + Permit C", and "Other Permits". Non-disclosed or unclear responses coded as missing.

Employment Status Question: 'Are you employed at a higher education institution?'

Other Demographic Variables

These variables will not be used for group comparisons later, thus the name "other".

Care Work

Question: 'Do you currently care for children, family members, or others besides your academic job?', with answer options: not quoted ; quoted.

Simplified into "care work" (if respondents indicated caring for children and/or family) or "no care work".

Employment Percentage

Question: 'What is your workload as a percentage according to all your current employment contracts at the higher education institution?'

Additional Non-Academic Job

Question: 'Do you have an additional non-academic paid job?'

General Mental Health

Question: 'In general, my mental health is ...'

General Mental Health by Age

General Mental Health by Gender

the 'other' category entails the non-binary response category or if both male and female gender were indicated

General Mental Health by Research Discipline

General Mental Health by Funding Source

General Mental Health by Position Type

General Mental Health by Employment Status

General Mental Health by Residence

Depression

We computed a depression score by summing the 7 items from the DASS-21 depression subscale. In our sample, this measure showed excellent internal consistency (Cronbach's alpha = .91), indicating that the items reliably measure the same underlying construct. A total of 62 observations were excluded from this analysis due to missing data on at least one of the depression items.

Following the clinical guidelines proposed by Nilges and Essau (2021), a sum score above 10 is considered indicative of elevated depressive symptoms and may be viewed as clinically relevant.

Depression by Age

Depression by Gender

the 'other' category entails the non-binary response category or if both male and female gender were indicated

Depression by Research Discipline

Depression by Funding Source

Depression by Position Type

Depression by Employment Status

Depression by Residence

Burnout

Question: 'I feel burned out from my work.'

Item developed and validated by West and colleagues (2009).

Burnout by Age

Burnout by Gender

the 'other' category entails the non-binary response category or if both male and female gender were indicated

Burnout by Research Discipline

Burnout by Funding Source

Burnout by Position Type

Burnout by Employment Status

Burnout by Residence

Awareness Resources

Awareness Resources by Age

Awareness Resources by Gender

the 'other' category entails the non-binary response category or if both male and female gender were indicated

Awareness Resources by Research Discipline

Awareness Resources by Funding Source

Awareness Resources by Position Type

Awareness Resources by Employment Status

Awareness Resources by Residence

Job Satisfaction

Question formulation:

Taking everything into consideration, how satisfied do you feel about your job as a whole?

Item developed and validated by Dolbier and colleagues (2005).

Job Satisfaction by Age

Job Satisfaction by Gender

the 'other' category entails the non-binary response category or if both male and female gender were indicated

Job Satisfaction by Research Discipline

Job Satisfaction by Funding Source

Job Satisfaction by Position Type

Job Satisfaction by Employment Status

Job Satisfaction by Residence

Quitting Intentions

Question: 'How often have you experienced thoughts of quitting your current position due to the working environment in the past year?'

Quitting Intentions by Age

Quitting Intentions by Gender

the 'other' category entails the non-binary response category or if both male and female gender were indicated

Quitting Intentions by Research Discipline

Quitting Intentions by Funding Source

Quitting Intentions by Position Type

Quitting Intentions by Employment Status

Quitting Intentions by Residence

Stress

Item formulation:

Stress means a situation in which a person feels tense, restless, nervous or anxious or is unable to sleep at night because their mind is troubled all the time. Do you feel this kind of stress these days?

Item developed and validated by Elo and colleagues (2003).

Stress by Age

Stress by Gender

the 'other' category entails the non-binary response category or if both male and female gender were indicated

Stress by Research Discipline

Stress by Funding Source

Stress by Position Type

Stress by Employment Status

Stress by Residence

Stressors

Stressor System

Question: 'To what degree is the following causing you stress currently?'

Stressor System by Age

Stressor System by Gender

the 'other' category entails the non-binary response category or if both male and female gender were indicated

the 'other' category entails the non-binary response category or if both male and female gender were indicated

Stressor System by Research Discipline

Stressor System by Funding Source

Stressor System by Position Type

Stressor System by Employment Status

Stressor System by Residence

Stressor Supervisor

Question: 'To what degree is the following causing you stress currently?'

Stressor Supervisor by Age

Stressor Supervisor by Gender

the 'other' category entails the non-binary response category or if both male and female gender were indicated

Stressor Supervisor by Research Discipline

Stressor Supervisor by Funding Source

Stressor Supervisor by Position Type

Stressor Supervisor by Employment Status

Stressor Supervisor by Residence

Stressor Colleagues

Question: 'To what degree is the following causing you stress currently?'

Stressor Colleagues by Age

Stressor Colleagues by Gender

the 'other' category entails the non-binary response category or if both male and female gender were indicated

Stressor Colleagues by Research Discipline

Stressor Colleagues by Funding Source

Stressor Colleagues by Position Type

Stressor Colleagues by Employment Status

Stressor Colleagues by Residence

Stressor Self-Management

Question: 'To what degree is the following causing you stress currently?'

Stressor Self-Management by Age

Stressor Self-Management by Gender

the 'other' category entails the non-binary response category or if both male and female gender were indicated

Stressor Self-Management by Research Discipline

Stressor Self-Management by Funding Source

Stressor Self-Management by Position Type

Stressor Self-Management by Employment Status

Stressor Self-Management by Residence

Stressor Private

Question: 'To what degree is the following causing you stress currently?'

Stressor Private by Age

Stressor Private by Gender

the 'other' category entails the non-binary response category or if both male and female gender were indicated

Stressor Private by Research Discipline

Stressor Private by Funding Source

Stressor Private by Position Type

Stressor Private by Employment Status

Stressor Private by Residence

Statements Regarding Supervisor

Question: 'To what extent do you agree with the following statements regarding your supervisor(s)?'

Supervisor by Age

■ Agree completely
 ■ Agree slightly
 ■ Neither agree nor disagree
 ■ Disagree slightly
 ■ Disagree completely

Supervisor by Gender

the 'other' category entails the non-binary response category or if both male and female gender were indicated

the 'other' category entails the non-binary response category or if both male and female gender were indicated

the 'other' category entails the non-binary response category or if both male and female gender were indicated

Supervisor by Research Discipline

Supervisor by Funding Source

Supervisor by Position Type

Supervisor by Employment Status

Supervisor by Residence

Statements Regarding Institution

Question: 'To what extent do you agree with the following statements regarding your institution / workplace?'

Institution by Age

Institution by Gender

the 'other' category entails the non-binary response category or if both male and female gender were indicated

the 'other' category entails the non-binary response category or if both male and female gender were indicated

Institution by Research Discipline

Institution by Funding Source

Institution by Position Type

Institution by Employment Status

Institution by Residence

Statements Regarding Work-Group

These workgroup-related questions were asked only if the respondents indicated to be in a working group, 79.53% (n = 1997) of the respondents.

Question: 'To what extent do you agree with the following statements regarding your working group?'

Workgroup by Age

Workgroup by Gender

the 'other' category entails the non-binary response category or if both male and female gender were indicated

Workgroup by Research Discipline

Workgroup by Funding Source

Workgroup by Position Type

Workgroup by Employment Status

Workgroup by Residence

Discrimination

Discrimination Experience

Question: 'In your position in Switzerland, have you ever...'

Discrimination Experience by Age

Discrimination Experience by Gender

the 'other' category entails the non-binary response category or if both male and female gender were indicated

the 'other' category entails the non-binary response category or if both male and female gender were indicated

Discrimination Experience by Research Discipline

Discrimination Experience by Funding Source

Discrimination Experience by Position Type

Discrimination Experience by Employment Status

Discrimination Experience by Residence

Sources of Discrimination Dimensions

Question: 'In cases where you have experienced or witnessed bullying, discrimination, harassment, or other unfair treatment, were such behaviors related to...'

This plot shows the responses of the subset of respondents (n = 2284; 90.7%), who indicated that they have experienced or witnessed bullying, discrimination, harassment, or other unfair treatment during their position in Switzerland. Each person could name multiple perceived sources of discrimination.

Questionable Research Practices

Question: 'Do you know of anyone at your research institution who performs one of the following questionable research practices?'

Questionable Research Practices by Age

Questionable Research Practices by Gender

the 'other' category entails the non-binary response category or if both male and female gender were indicated

Questionable Research Practices by Research Discipline

■ Not applicable
 ■ Prefer not to say
 ■ Uncertain/do not know
 ■ No
 ■ Yes

Questionable Research Practices by Funding Source

■ Not applicable
 ■ Prefer not to say
 ■ Uncertain/do not know
 ■ No
 ■ Yes

Questionable Research Practices by Position Type

■ Not applicable
 ■ Prefer not to say
 ■ Uncertain/do not know
 ■ No
 ■ Yes

Questionable Research Practices by Employment Status

■ Not applicable
 ■ Prefer not to say
 ■ Uncertain/do not know
 ■ No
 ■ Yes

Questionable Research Practices by Residence

Not applicable Prefer not to say Uncertain/do not know No Yes

Pressures to Perform Questionable Research Practices

Question: 'Have any of the following groups of people pressured you into questionable research practices?'

Respondents could select multiple categories. This figure presents all reported sources combined, showing the total number of different sources of pressure to engage in questionable research practices. n = 1816 reported that no one pressured them, n = 285 indicated one source, and n = 244 reported multiple sources.

Effects of Pressures to Perform Questionable Research Practices on Mental Health

Question: 'To what extent do you feel your mental health is negatively impacted by pressures from any of the previously named groups to engage in questionable research practices?'

Effects of Pressures to Perform Questionable Research Practices on Mental Health by Age

Effects of Pressures to Perform Questionable Research Practices on Mental Health by Gender

the 'other' category entails the non-binary response category or if both male and female gender were indicated

Effects of Pressures to Perform Questionable Research Practices on Mental Health by Research Discipline

Effects of Pressures to Perform Questionable Research Practices on Mental Health by Funding Source

Effects of Pressures to Perform Questionable Research Practices on Mental Health by Position Type

Effects of Pressures to Perform Questionable Research Practices on Mental Health by Employment Status

Effects of Pressures to Perform Questionable Research Practices on Mental Health by Residence

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